

1 **National climate change impact assessments underestimate the**
2 **potential of autonomous adaptation**

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30

31 **Abstract**

32
33 Central Europe is projected to lose up to 25% of its crop productivity by 2050 because of
34 climate change, posing significant challenges to agricultural systems and food security.
35 Effective adaptation strategies must consider not only domestic impacts but also global
36 climate effects, including international trade dynamics. We performed a multilevel analysis
37 of climate change impacts on agriculture, using the Czech Republic, a landlocked, crop
38 production-based economy with an open market, as a case study. We integrated the
39 global biosphere management model (GLOBIOM) with the gridded global crop model
40 EPIC-IIASA. Climate impacts were projected with five global circulation models under
41 three climate scenarios, with and without CO₂ fertilization, and applied in national, EU-
42 regional, and global productivity change scenarios. The results show that national-only
43 assessments underestimate both risks and opportunities: production is projected to
44 decline by up to 9% when global interactions are excluded but to increase by up to 8%
45 when trade and market effects are included. Autonomous adaptation mechanisms, such
46 as cropland reallocation, shifts in management intensity, and trade adjustments, buffer
47 biophysical yield losses and improve economic outcomes. Neglecting global interactions
48 in national climate change assessments increases the risk of maladaptation and policy
49 inefficiencies. The incorporation of international market linkages enhances the ability to
50 design robust adaptation strategies, enabling countries such as the Czech Republic to
51 maximize resilience while minimizing environmental and socioeconomic trade-offs.

52

53 **Keywords**

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55 Climate change, Adaptation, Agricultural trade, Czech Republic, Integrated assessment,
56 Food security

57

58 **Introduction**

59
60 Climate change is expected to pose substantial agricultural challenges in Central Europe,
61 with potential crop productivity declining by up to 25% by mid-century. (Pörtner et al.
62 2022). Maize yields can decrease by as much as 25%, whereas wheat losses may reach
63 15%, depending on the extent of CO₂ fertilization between 2040 and 2069 (Eitzinger et al.
64 2013; Webber et al. 2018). Robust adaptation strategies must be developed to address
65 these anticipated agricultural losses. A key question is whether focusing solely on the
66 direct, national impacts of climate change provides a sufficient foundation for planning and
67 decision-making (Ercin et al. 2021). While national climate change assessments are
68 crucial for designing adaptation strategies, the global nature and interconnectedness of
69 climate change effects and agricultural markets may significantly influence national
70 resilience and adaptation efforts (Ercin et al. 2019). Ignoring the effects of climate change
71 on global agricultural production and international trade when national adaptation
72 strategies are developed increases the likelihood of maladaptation; as such, assessments
73 risk underestimating or overestimating the impacts of national climate change (Pörtner et
74 al. 2022).

75

76 Key players in the global agricultural market have relied on national and global agricultural
77 models to assess impacts and develop adaptation plans, such as those for the United

78 States (e.g., Baker et al., 2018), Brazil (e.g., Zilli et al., 2020), and the European Union
79 (EU) (e.g., Blanco et al., 2017). Moreover, 18 countries have started incorporating global
80 frameworks to better understand and address challenges in the agricultural sector and
81 associated linkages to climate mitigation and adaptation, for example, via the Food,
82 Agriculture, Biodiversity, Land-Use, and Energy (FABLE) (FABLE 2019). However, in the
83 case of the Czech Republic, climate change impact assessments are based
84 predominantly on country- or region-scale modeling approaches. Although the Czech
85 Republic does not play a dominant role in the global agricultural market, its agricultural
86 sector remains an essential component of the national economy and rural livelihoods
87 (Prochazka et al. 2023). Furthermore, changes in crop suitability and agricultural area
88 expansion may position it as a more significant regional player within the EU as a
89 consistent food supplier (Papadimitriou et al. 2019).

90
91 Czech agriculture is a cereal-based sector, where wheat production represented 62% of
92 cereal production in 2024, followed by barley with 22% and maize with 9% (CZSO 2025).
93 The Czech Republic's agricultural trade is strongly oriented toward the European Union,
94 with approximately four-fifths of all exports directed to EU Member States and only a minor
95 share reaching markets outside the EU (Zábojníková and Kamenický 2024) Germany
96 remains its key trading partner. Although cereals account for more than half of domestic
97 agricultural output, the Czech Republic overall is a net importer of agricultural products
98 (Zábojníková and Kamenický 2024). The impacts of climate change on Czech agriculture
99 have been extensively studied via biophysical models focused on single commodities
100 such as maize (Pavlik et al. 2019), barley, and wheat (Trnka et al. 2004a; Thaler et al.
101 2012; Eitzinger et al. 2013), as well as livestock (Potopová et al. 2023) and provisioning
102 ecosystem services (Lorencová et al. 2013). Some studies have also modeled multiple
103 key crops (Hlavinka et al. 2015; Pohanková et al. 2022; Pohanková et al. 2024) or
104 analyzed agroclimatic indicators (Eitzinger et al. 2013) at specific sites. Papadimitriou et
105 al. (2019) incorporated transnational market interactions into assessments of the Czech
106 Republic, and a European-scale model was used to simulate variations in imports and
107 exports on the basis of shared socioeconomic pathways (O'Neill et al. 2014). Potopová et
108 al. (2023) used climate projections to determine the future water consumption of livestock
109 in the country, and more recently, (Poláková et al. 2025) integrated the feedback loop
110 from local to global by integrating the national yield response into a general equilibrium
111 model. Despite their contributions, these studies share common limitations. First, they fail
112 to capture climate change impacts outside their spatial domains, restricting their ability to
113 assess the Czech Republic's relative competitiveness within the EU. Second, they omit
114 or aggregate agricultural market dynamics beyond Europe, such as international trade,
115 leading to a biased understanding of the country's autonomous adaptation potential.

116
117 Building on the approaches of Baker et al. (2018) and Papadimitriou et al. (2019), this
118 study develops a comprehensive, multilevel framework to assess the Czech agricultural
119 sector's autonomous adaptation to climate change. We hypothesize that global climate
120 change impacts and international market dynamics play critical roles in shaping the
121 effectiveness of national adaptation strategies. We evaluate the Czech agricultural
122 sector's autonomous adaptation potential by integrating national, regional, and global
123 drivers through two globally consistent modeling tools: a partial equilibrium model of
124 agriculture and forestry and a gridded global crop model. This framework enables us to

125 quantify how national climate impacts interact with global productivity changes and market
126 responses. This study aims (1) to assess the direct impacts of climate change on Czech
127 agriculture; (2) to evaluate the limitations of adaptation assessments that rely solely on
128 national-scale climate impact studies; and (3) to assess the autonomous adaptation
129 potential of the Czech agricultural sector when both national and global drivers are
130 considered together. By explicitly representing interactions between the Czech Republic
131 and international markets, this approach provides a more comprehensive understanding
132 of the conditions under which autonomous adaptation may emerge.
133

134

135 **Methods**

136

137 **Models**

138

139 We apply the global biosphere management model (GLOBIOM) (Havlík et al. 2014), a
140 partial equilibrium model that represents the global agriculture, forestry, and bioenergy
141 sectors. GLOBIOM has been widely applied to assess climate change impacts and
142 mitigation pathways at the global (Nelson et al. 2014; Hasegawa et al. 2018; Fujimori et
143 al. 2019) and EU levels, including the recent impact assessment of the European
144 Commission’s Fit-for-55 package (EC 2021). Unlike models that aggregate countries into
145 broader regional blocks, GLOBIOM explicitly represents market relationships among EU
146 Member States, making it particularly suitable for national-scale analyses (Frank et al.
147 2015). It is also included among the IPCC’s Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs), where
148 it complements the MESSAGE model by representing the land-based mitigation sector
149 (Krey et al. 2020) and climate impacts (Awais et al. 2024). Beyond food production,
150 GLOBIOM incorporates land competition with forestry as well as demand for feed and
151 bioenergy (Havlík et al. 2011; Havlík et al. 2014), enabling analysis of cross-sectoral trade-
152 offs and cobenefits. Its detailed representation of agricultural commodities, including
153 wheat, barley, and maize, provides a robust basis for evaluating cereal-based agricultural
154 systems such as those in the Czech Republic. Additional information about the global and
155 European versions of GLOBIOM was reported by Havlík et al. (2014) and Frank et al.
156 (2015), respectively.
157

158 GLOBIOM represents the supply, demand and commodity markets for the agricultural
159 sector. Commodity markets and international trade are represented for 57 economic
160 regions, one for each EU member state and the UK, and 29 additional regions outside the
161 EU. Within each region, a representative consumer optimizes consumption on the basis
162 of preferences and commodity prices, while producers maximize margins, and GLOBIOM
163 is used to solve for the market equilibrium scheme that achieves overall welfare
164 maximization. The supply side of the model follows a bottom-up approach using detailed
165 spatial data for land cover, land use, management systems, and biophysical and technical
166 costs. The EU28 is represented at the NUTS2 level, ensuring fine-scale detail. Crop,
167 livestock, and forest production activities are considered via biophysical modeling
168 frameworks. The crop model EPIC is used to compute crop productivity, fertilizer
169 requirements, and irrigation management practices. The European crop sector is modeled
170 via crop rotations for 18 key crops, derived from EUROSTAT statistics at the NUTS2 level,

171 with the CropRota model (Schönhart et al. 2011). The livestock sector and its production
172 system parameters are modeled with the RUMINANT model (Herrero et al. 2013). Primary
173 forest productivity and harvesting costs are estimated via the global forest model (G4M)
174 (Kindermann et al. 2008). Six dynamically modeled land use types (cropland, grassland,
175 short-rotation tree plantations, managed forests, natural forests, and other natural land)
176 can be converted on the basis of the demand and profitability of land-based activities.
177 Within Europe, no deforestation for agricultural expansion is assumed because of
178 restrictive land use legislation (Bauer et al. 2004).

179

180

181 **Autonomous adaptation**

182

183 Climate change adaptation refers to “the process of adjustment to actual or expected
184 climate and its effects” (Pörtner et al. 2022). The adjustment can be explicitly planned or
185 occur spontaneously, triggered by farmer or market changes as a response to climate
186 change—referred to as autonomous adaptation (Pörtner et al. 2022; Maskell et al. 2025).
187 In GLOBIOM, autonomous adaptation to climate-induced changes in crop yields can be
188 explored through adjustments in production, consumption, and trade patterns. Supply-
189 side adaptation occurs through land reallocation by expanding cropland into other land
190 cover types, altering crop shares at the national level, or shifting between low-input and
191 high-input management systems (Leclère et al. 2014). Consumers adapt by modifying
192 both the quantity and structure of food consumption on the basis of price signals (Mosnier
193 et al. 2014). International trade serves as another crucial adaptation mechanism. Climate-
194 induced changes in productivity may shift comparative advantages across regions,
195 enabling trade to redistribute surplus production from favorable regions to deficit regions
196 (Janssens et al. 2020). In GLOBIOM, economic regions adjust trade quantities and trading
197 partnerships to buffer productivity shocks and maintain market balance.

198

199 **Climate change impacts**

200

201 To represent the effects of climate change on crop productivity, the global gridded crop
202 model EPIC-IIASA (Balkovič et al. 2013) was run in conjunction with five distinct global
203 circulation models (GCMs) from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6
204 (CMIP6) (O’Neill et al. 2016a; Jägermeyr et al. 2021). We selected the three climate
205 scenarios from the latest protocol of the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison
206 Project (ISI-MIP) ISIMIP3b (Eyring et al. 2016). They consisted of a combination of the
207 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) and Representative Concentration Pathways
208 (RCPs), SSP1–2.6, SSP3–7.0, and SSP5–8.5 (Gidden et al., 2019), simulated with
209 climate data driven by five general circulation models (GCMs): GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-
210 LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, and UKESM1-0-LL. Supplementary Table 1 provides
211 further details about each model. SSP1-2.6 describes a pathway with a mitigation effort
212 to keep the level of warming below 2°C by 2100, which is consistent with the Paris
213 Agreement; SSP3-7.0 represents an unmitigated pathway, whereas SSP5-8.5 represents
214 the highest emission pathway (O’Neill et al. 2016b).

215

216 EPIC-IIASA estimated the productivity of four key crops (maize, rice, soy, and wheat).
217 Productivity for 17 additional crops (including barley, silage maize, cotton, and sugar beet)

218 was computed on the basis of their C3/C4 photosynthesis pathways, following the
219 approach of Janssens et al. (2020) (Supplementary Table 2). The projected climate
220 impacts were then incorporated into GLOBIOM as productivity changes compared to
221 those in the year 2000. The EPIC-IIASA projections were available at a 0.5×0.5 degree
222 resolution and upscaled to 2×2 degree cells, matching the resolution of GLOBIOM's land
223 units, using a weighted average based on the respective crop areas in the year 2000.
224 Livestock impacts were modeled indirectly through changes in feed production rather than
225 explicit productivity impacts.

226
227

228 **Scenario design**

229

230 We implemented three climate impact scenarios to assess the limitations of adaptation
231 assessments that rely solely on national-scale climate impact studies. In the national
232 scenarios, productivity changes were applied only to Czech production systems, keeping
233 yields elsewhere consistent with socioeconomic assumptions. In the regional scenarios,
234 changes extended to the EU27, including the UK. Both scenarios accounted for
235 endogenous changes in global productivity and market interactions. In the global scenario,
236 productivity impacts were applied across all the regions modeled (Table 1.). This scenario
237 design isolates the effects of country- and region-scale assessments from global-scale
238 impacts, enabling comparisons of climate-induced productivity changes. All the scenarios
239 included the same autonomous adaptation options, although economically optimal
240 adaptations differed on the basis of whether national, regional, or global effects were
241 modeled.

242

243 To assess the direct effects of climate change on agriculture, we deliberately decoupled
244 the SSP and RCP dimensions. Unlike biophysical impact models such as EPIC-IIASA,
245 economic models such as GLOBIOM capture major socioeconomic drivers—including
246 population growth, GDP, technological change, and food demand—which allows us to
247 isolate the influence of different radiative forcing trajectories while keeping socioeconomic
248 conditions constant across all scenarios (Rogelj et al. 2018). Although the SSP–RCP
249 pairing in CMIP6 enables models such as EPIC-IIASA to generate integrated biophysical
250 and socioeconomic narratives, economic models offer greater flexibility to separate and
251 independently analyze the contributions of each dimension, especially not additional
252 mitigation from the land-based sector associated with the SSP trajectories. For this
253 reason, all climate impact scenarios in GLOBIOM are evaluated under SSP2
254 socioeconomic conditions (O'Neill et al. 2016a); in this way, we also understand in
255 isolation the autonomous response of the agricultural sector.

256

257 Following this logic and to ensure consistency and robustness, we use the notation *SSP–*
258 *RCP* for the direct outputs from EPIC-IIASA and *RCP* alone for the direct outputs from
259 GLOBIOM. A comparison of the results across these scenarios reveals important
260 differences in national crop production patterns and in the autonomous adaptation
261 responses expressed through market indicators

262

263

Climate Impact Scenario	Regional Extent	Rationale	Climate Scenarios	GCMs
National	Czech Republic	Climate impacts are applied to crop productivity in the Czech Republic. The rest of the world retains SSP2 productivity levels.	SSP1–2.6 w/o CO ₂ SSP1–2.6 w/CO ₂	GFDL-ESM4 IPSL-CM6A-LR
Regional	EU27 + UK	Climate impacts are applied to crop productivity in the EU27 and the UK. The rest of the world retains SSP2 productivity levels.	SSP3–7.0 w/o CO ₂ SSP3–7.0 w/CO ₂ SSP5–8.5 w/o CO ₂ SSP5–8.5 w/CO ₂	MPI-ESM1-2-HR MRI-ESM2-0 UKESM1-0-LL
Global	World	Climate impacts are applied to global crop productivity.		

Table 1. Climate impact scenarios assessed in this study, showing the regional extent, rationale, climate scenarios, and CMIP6 general circulation models (GCMs) used to evaluate the effects of biophysical climate change on crop productivity.

Results

Our results focus on projected relative changes to the no-climate-change scenario for different agricultural indicators in the Czech Republic, the EU28, and globally by 2050. The biophysical effects of climate change on yields (see Figure 1a) vary from -27% to 6% across crops, scenarios, and climate models. Compared with the maize yield, the wheat yield declines less severely in these scenarios, ranging from -5% (RCP 8.5) to 6% (RCP 7.0), whereas the maize yield declines by -22% (RCP 8.5) to 5% (RCP 2.6). Overall, the effects of climate change on crop yields in the Czech Republic follow a pattern similar to that observed for wheat (-5% to +10%), reflecting the dominance of C3 crops in Czech agricultural production. Wheat (C3) and maize (C4) both show the greatest yield declines under the high-emission scenario RCP8.5 without the CO₂ fertilization effect. The wheat and maize yields decrease from -12% to 2% and from -27% to 3%, respectively, when CO₂ fertilization effects are not considered. UKESM1-0-LL consistently projects the most negative impacts, whereas GFDL-ESM4 shows the most positive impacts across crops and climate scenarios. The large variation among GCMs can be attributed to differences in their CO₂ concentration pathways in the CMIP6 experiment and their climate sensitivity. By the end of the century, UKESM1-0-LL registers the greatest temperature increase, whereas GFDL-ESM4 is the lowest across all climate scenarios (Jägermeyr et al. 2021).

290
 291 **Fig. 1.** Effects of climate change on crop yields and agricultural indicators in 2050 in the Czech Republic under climate
 292 and impact scenarios. (a) Biophysical yield changes relative to a no-climate-change baseline (%) simulated by EPIC-
 293 IIASA for wheat, maize and aggregated crops under SSP1-2.6, SSP3-7.0 and SSP5-8.5, each with and without CO₂
 294 fertilization. The bars show the multimodel means (CMIP6 ensemble average), and the symbols denote individual
 295 general circulation models (GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, and UKESM1-0-LL). (b)
 296 Changes (%) in sectoral indicators, yield, area, production, consumption, prices and net trade under national, regional
 297 (EU) and global climate-impact contexts. Boxplots indicate interquartile ranges, whiskers show ranges excluding
 298 outliers, black lines denote medians, and filled dots mark means. The results aggregate 30 climate scenarios (n = 30)

299

Economic response to the effects of climate change in the Czech Republic

An overview of how the biophysical effects of climate change on yields propagate across agricultural indicators under different climate impact scenarios is shown in Figure 1b. GLOBIOM transfers the initial effect on yields to the response of agricultural indicators via supply and demand adjustments to agricultural production in the country. Markets, production, and consumption patterns adjust to the assumed yield and trade conditions, with the goal of maximizing total economic surplus by 2050 globally, including in the Czech Republic. Producers respond to climate change primarily through agricultural area expansion, which averages 3%, rather than intensified management practices (-0.08%) (see Figure 1b, global climate impact scenario and the olive-green point). The area changes remain within $\pm 5\%$ across all scenario dimensions, reaching 14% under the most extreme scenario (RCP 8.5 without CO₂ fertilization effects). In contrast, yield changes are small, are centered mostly at approximately 0% and show limited variability across scenarios. The combined area increase and stable yield result in a mean production increase of 3%, with changes within $\pm 10\%$. Consumption in the Czech Republic is stable across most scenarios, and only a small change (3%) is expected under RCP 8.5 without CO₂ fertilization effects. Net trade (calculated as exports minus imports) displays the greatest variation in all the indicators, with changes ranging from -8% to 27%, depending on the scenario. On average, net trade increases by 10%, indicating a net export surplus in response to climate change effects.

To investigate the drivers of heterogeneity in the selected indicators induced by climate change, an in-depth analysis with GLOBIOM is needed. The univariate regression lines of the selected indicators plotted against the biophysical effect on yields are shown in Figure 2. The slope coefficient reflects the local response and can be understood as the ability of a variable to change, interpreted as adaptive capacity. A value of 1 can be interpreted as a percentage change in the impact of climate change on yields in response to an equivalent percentage change in a given indicator. The intercept coefficient can be interpreted as a local change driven by indirect climate change effects and price effects transmitted by international markets. An intercept value other than 0 suggests that local changes arise from effects in other regions transmitted via price effects through international trade (Nelson et al. 2014). The slope and intercept coefficients for each climate impact scenario are also reported in Supplementary Table 3.

The yield in the Czech Republic appears unresponsive in terms of productivity management. With a slope close to 1 and an intercept close to 0, there is no additional compensation through management for climate change impacts on yield (see Figure 2c). The yield shows a slight local effect on crop reallocation between C3 and C4 crops because of differential climate change impacts (Supplementary Table 5). The area change shows a negative relationship between biophysical productivity and area, indicating a strong response in the Czech Republic. The area of specific crops is expected to decrease as the productivity of the crops increases. Climate change has led to a decrease in the cultivated areas of most impacted crops, and losses in production have been offset by imports from more favorable areas in the EU28. The same inverse relationship and market reallocation trend are shown by the production regression line but are less responsive than the area changes are, with

347 a smaller slope and intercept. The increase in production for crops is positively impacted
 348 by climate change, and for negatively impacted crops, production decreases and imports
 349 increase. Exports and imports are positively related to changes in biophysical yield.
 350 Exports are more responsive than are imports, with the highest intercept value indicating
 351 that the increase in exports is driven by the reallocation of production shares in the EU28
 352 and is less dependent on national yield and area responses. The consumption response
 353 is relatively small, and it displays a negative relationship with climate change impacts.

354
 355 **Fig. 2. Economic responses to biophysical yield changes in the Czech Republic under three climate impact**
 356 **scenarios (a: national, b: regional, and c: global) for 2050.** Each panel shows the percentage change in economic
 357 variables plotted against biophysical yield changes (%). The black dots represent changes in production, whereas the
 358 colored lines indicate univariate regressions for selected variables: area (green), consumption (red), exports (orange),
 359 imports (dashed orange), production (purple), prices (blue), biophysical yield (black) and yield (dotted black).

360
 361 Hence, the response to climate change in the Czech Republic occurs predominantly on
 362 the supply side through management intensity, cultivated land reallocation, and trade
 363 adaptation.

364 Comparing domestic, regional and global climate impact scenarios

365
 366 The responses of agricultural indicators across different climate scenarios are shown in
 367 Figure 1b. The purple bars correspond to the climate impacts only in the Czech Republic,
 368 the gray bars correspond to the climate impacts in the EU28, and the yellow bars
 369 correspond to the climate impacts globally. The means and standard deviations for each
 370 climate impact scenario are presented in Supplementary Fig. 1. When shifting from
 371 national to regional and global climate change impact scenarios, the variability and
 372 response of agricultural indicators differ.
 373
 374

375 The yield is not strongly affected by shifting climate impacts. On average, the yield
376 decreases by 0.6% in the national scenario to 0.08% in the global scenario. However, the
377 national scenario shows greater variability (SD: 3.2). In contrast, the area progressively
378 increases from 1% to 3%, with the greatest variability associated with the global impact
379 scenario (SD: 3.2). Changes in production occur in response to area expansion, with the
380 greatest effect occurring in the global impact scenario. Hence, the overall effect on
381 production is positive in the regional and global impact scenarios. The greatest variability
382 occurs when impacts are isolated to the Czech Republic. In this case, production is
383 projected to decrease to 9% in the most severe scenario without CO₂ fertilization effects,
384 in contrast to a 4% decrease when CO₂ is considered. When climate change impacts are
385 considered globally, the negative response in production is less pronounced, with
386 production increasing between 0.1% and 8% in most climate scenarios. On the demand
387 side, consumption remains unresponsive to differences in climate impact scenarios. Net
388 trade varies greatly across national and global assessments. No effect in response to
389 climate change is observed in the national impact scenario (1%, SD: 14), whereas net
390 trade increases progressively in the regional (6%, SD: 6.5) and global (10%, SD: 7.2)
391 scenarios.

392
393 The relationship between the yield response to biophysical changes due to climate effects
394 remains the same across the three impact scenarios (Figure 2a, b, and c, dotted black
395 line). However, the area response varies greatly among impact scenarios. While in the
396 regional and global climate impact scenarios, area displays an inverse relationship with
397 variations in the biophysical yield, in the national scenario, area has a positive relationship
398 with changes in biophysical yield, indicating a less responsive relationship and a reduced
399 effect of international price transmission. Moreover, national and regional climate impact
400 scenarios are positively related to production, with a limited response and a generally
401 stable trend in the Czech Republic. Consumption remains unresponsive to climate change
402 in all the scenarios, whereas import changes display a negative relationship in the national
403 impact scenario, with a decrease in imports as national productivity increases because of
404 climate change. Although supply-side autonomous adaptation mechanisms remain the
405 most responsive to climate change impacts across all impact scenarios, the behavior of
406 production differs when climate change impacts are applied globally.
407

Indicator	RCP 2.6		RCP 7.0		RCP 8.5		RCP 8.5 x GCM				
	w CO ₂	no CO ₂	w CO ₂	no CO ₂	w CO ₂	no CO ₂	MRI-ESM2-0	GFDL-ESM4	MPI-ESM1-2-HR	IPSL-CM6A-LR	UKESM1-0-LL
Biophysical crop yield	0.42%	-1.27%	1.75%	-1.76%	0.40%	-4.54%	1.04%	-4.13%	2.70%	2.19%	0.08%
Crop yield	0.43%	-1.98%	1.69%	-2.46%	-0.17%	-5.05%	1.03%	-4.63%	2.52%	2.04%	-0.22%
Crop production	0.36%	2.57%	1.12%	4.48%	3.20%	5.67%	0.43%	4.47%	1.88%	1.23%	1.30%
Livestock production	-0.04%	-2.18%	-0.06%	-2.21%	-1.30%	-2.13%	-0.56%	-2.16%	-2.61%	-0.17%	-3.32%
Cropland	-0.07%	4.64%	-0.57%	7.11%	3.38%	11.29%	-0.59%	9.54%	-0.63%	-0.79%	1.53%
Grassland	0.00%	-2.15%	0.02%	-2.15%	-2.04%	-2.15%	0.07%	-2.15%	-2.05%	0.03%	-2.13%
Food consumption from crops	0.00%	-0.07%	-0.33%	-0.06%	-0.05%	-0.18%	0.00%	-0.12%	-0.30%	-0.31%	-0.41%
Food consumption from livestock	-0.00%	-0.26%	-0.00%	-0.30%	-0.00%	-0.39%	0.00%	-0.39%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Feed consumption	-0.10%	-0.59%	-0.12%	-0.63%	0.03%	-0.54%	-0.68%	-0.50%	-1.05%	-0.26%	-1.67%
Crop exports	2.41%	5.75%	3.75%	6.65%	4.75%	8.45%	0.97%	5.86%	6.78%	4.21%	4.01%
Livestock exports	-0.21%	-9.25%	-0.19%	-9.19%	-5.49%	-8.82%	-2.39%	-8.90%	-11.06%	-0.69%	-14.02%
Crop imports	3.02%	1.64%	2.88%	-3.96%	-2.84%	-5.34%	-1.79%	-5.95%	4.32%	2.41%	-0.97%
Livestock imports	-0.10%	-1.80%	0.13%	-1.67%	0.10%	-2.28%	0.01%	-2.14%	0.16%	0.05%	0.23%
Crop prices	0.24%	0.62%	0.06%	0.90%	0.30%	0.95%	0.13%	1.11%	-0.35%	-0.12%	0.18%
Livestock prices	-0.34%	0.14%	-0.27%	1.48%	-4.16%	3.18%	-0.42%	2.02%	-3.83%	-3.24%	-1.93%
Crop self-sufficiency	0.34%	1.11%	0.77%	1.96%	1.36%	2.66%	0.61%	1.98%	1.53%	0.96%	1.40%
Livestock self-sufficiency	-0.04%	-1.93%	-0.06%	-1.93%	-1.30%	-1.76%	-0.56%	-1.80%	-2.61%	-0.17%	-3.32%

■ Not Agreement ■ National and global agreement ■ National, regional and global agreement
■ Regional and global agreement ■ National and regional agreement

408
409 **Fig. 3 Agreement in the direction of percentage changes (positive or negative) in selected agricultural and food**
410 **system indicators in different climate scenarios.** The values represent the percentage changes in global climate
411 impact scenarios in reference to the value in the no-climate-change baseline, and the colors indicate the level of
412 agreement in the sign of change across national, regional, and global scales. Red represents no agreement, orange
413 indicates regional and global agreement, green represents national and regional agreement, yellow represents national
414 and global agreement, and blue agreement across all three scales. Indicators are assessed under the RCP2.6, RCP7.0,
415 and RCP8.5 scenarios, with and without CO₂ fertilization effects.

416 The level of agreement in the direction of changes (positive or negative) across national,
417 regional, and global climate impacts for selected agricultural and food system indicators
418 under various climate scenarios is shown in Figure 3. The level of agreement refers to the
419 consistency in the sign of changes, and the values represent the percentage change in
420 the global climate impact scenario. Strong agreement (blue) is observed for variables such
421 as crop self-sufficiency, livestock self-sufficiency, and crop yields, particularly in scenarios
422 that include CO₂ effects, reflecting consistent increases in crop-related indicators due to
423 CO₂ fertilization. In contrast, indicators such as grassland area, food consumption from
424 livestock, and feed consumption frequently display no agreement (red), indicating high
425 variability in responses across scales, especially in the national impact scenario. The trade
426 variables exhibit mixed levels of agreement: crop exports often align regionally and
427 globally (orange) under high-emission scenarios such as RCP 8.5, whereas livestock
428 exports and imports show considerable disagreement. Land use changes exhibit relatively
429 consistent agreement for croplands (often blue or orange) but limited agreement for
430 grasslands, highlighting regional variability. Notably, high-emission scenarios (RCP8.5)
431 tend to be characterized by greater uncertainty, with frequent divergence among the

432
 433 **Fig. 4 Decomposition of climate change impacts, autonomous adaptations, and total effects on crop production**
 434 **in the Czech Republic, expressed as absolute changes relative to a no-climate-change scenario (1000 tons).**
 435 The results are divided into three components: (1) climate impact (CC) – changes in productivity due to biophysical
 436 effects; (2) autonomous adaptations (MGMTs) – adjustments through shifts in agricultural management systems; and
 437 (3) total impact (PROD) – combined effects on crop production, including changes in yield (TOT YLD) and cropland
 438 area (TOT AREA) under different climate impact scenarios at the (a) national, (b) regional, and (c) global scales. The
 439 bars represent projections under the UKESM1-0-LL RCP8.5 scenario, with error bars indicating variability across GCMs
 440 (red) and RCPs (black). The black dots represent results excluding CO₂ fertilization effects.

441 national, regional, and global impact scenarios, especially for trade and consumption
442 patterns. Livestock-related indicators remain highly uncertain across impact scenarios
443 because of the variable response of cropland expansion. As cropland expansion is driven
444 by the effects of climate change in the rest of the world, which is transmitted through price
445 effects in the Czech Republic, land use shifts from grassland to cropland occur (see
446 Supplementary Table 7); therefore, the production of beef and milk are consistent among
447 the scenarios in which climate change impacts are considered globally. Overall, the results
448 demonstrate that while some indicators exhibit consistent trends across scales, others,
449 particularly those related to trade and consumption, remain highly uncertain and
450 dependent on the scale at which climate change impacts are considered.
451

452 **Impact of autonomous adaptation on production and trade**

453

454 The effects of climate change on yield reduced Czech agricultural production from -526 to
455 342 kilotons (first column of Figure 4). The equivalent reduction in production as the level
456 of warming increased across the RCP is robust (black error bars in Figure 4), but there is
457 considerable uncertainty across the GCM scenarios (red error bars in Figure 4). Without
458 the CO₂ fertilization effect, the decline is as high as 1210 kilotons (black dots in Figure 4).
459 The individual effects on the production of autonomous responses, such as shifts in
460 management systems (MGMT), the overall effects of yields due to climate change and
461 management system productivity (TOT YLD), and area expansion (TOT AREA) (middle
462 columns of Figure 4), were based on the findings of Leclère et al. (2014). We estimate
463 that shifts in management systems play a marginal role in production (second column of
464 Figure 4). Production is expected to decline from -4 to -74 kilotons (see Figure 4c) and -
465 71 kilotons without the effect of CO₂. These results are robust among the RCP and GCM
466 scenarios. However, the effect of area expansion is considerably greater than that of shifts
467 in management systems.
468

469 An increase in production of up to 1187 kilotons is expected because of area expansion,
470 and the effect almost doubles when the CO₂ fertilization effect is not considered, with a
471 gain in production of up to 2263 kilotons. The increase in production due to area expansion
472 is enough to offset the losses due to climate change effects (last column of Figure 4). The
473 overall effect of autonomous adaptation has a positive effect on production by 610
474 kilotons, which doubles without the CO₂ fertilization effect, reaching 1027 kilotons. The
475 final positive impact is robust across GCMs. However, under UKESM1-0-LL RCP 2.6 and
476 RCP 7.0, there are reductions in the production of 17 and 330 kilotons, respectively.
477

478 The impacts of autonomous adaptation on production in the national and regional climate
479 impact scenarios are shown in Figures 4a and 4b, respectively. The shift in management
480 systems remains marginal among climate impact scenarios. However, the impacts on
481 area expansion and total impact on production differ vastly. When impacts are isolated to
482 the Czech Republic, the overall effect on production is more negative than that under
483 global and regional climate impact scenarios, ranging from -499 to 698 kilotons. The
484 losses are driven by a combined effect of a slight increase in production due to
485 management changes (from -103 to 13 kilotons) and insufficient area expansion (from -
486 16 to 483 kilotons) to compensate for the overall losses in production due to climate
487 change.

488
489 When the region is impacted by climate change, Czech production remains negatively
490 impacted, declining to as much as -473 kilotons and increasing to 446 kilotons, depending
491 on the GCM and RCP combination. The losses are due to the limited effects of
492 management (from -68 to 16 kilotons) and larger area expansions (from -38 to 779
493 kilotons) compared with those observed for the national climate impact scenario. Despite
494 all autonomous adaptation options being available in GLOBIOM for all climate impact
495 scenarios, the economically optimal combination of options differs when shifting from
496 national to regional and global impacts. The area of Czech cropland progressively
497 increased in response to new market configurations when regional and global climate
498 change affected agricultural yields.

499
500 The net bilateral trade relationships between the Czech Republic and the rest of the EU28
501 and the rest of the world for aggregate crop commodities are shown in Figure 5. The EU28
502 was divided into 4 regions to best represent the flows to and from the Czech Republic,
503 and the trade flows outside the EU28 were determined, combined, and denoted as ‘the
504 rest of the world’ (RoW) (Supplementary Fig. 2). The size of the lines in the chord diagram
505 represents the total trade flow under each climate impact scenario and the no-climate
506 change scenario. We use the revealed comparative advantage (RCA) indicator, which is
507 based on the Ricardian comparative advantage concept, to assess the relative positions
508 of Czech agricultural commodities in the international market (Balassa 1965). In the RCA
509 approach, trade flows are used to calculate a country’s relative advantage or disadvantage
510 in the international agricultural market. A value greater than 1 indicates a comparative
511 advantage for a commodity, whereas a value less than 1 indicates a comparative
512 disadvantage. The RCA values for wheat, maize, barley, rapeseed, and potatoes, the
513 primary commodities traded by the Czech Republic, are shown in Supplementary Fig. 3.

514
515 The total trade flows are greater under climate change than under the no-climate change
516 scenario, with the greatest increase observed when climate change impacts are
517 considered globally. The greatest export trade flow is observed between the Czech
518 Republic and Western European countries in the regional and global scenarios and with
519 the rest of the world in the national scenario. The Czech Republic is projected to export
520 2.2, 2.2, 2.3, and 2.3 million tons of product to other Western European countries under
521 the no climate change scenario and the national, regional, and global climate impact
522 scenarios, respectively. The Czech Republic displays variability in terms of its RCA values
523 under different climate change scenarios and for different crops. Barley, rapeseed, and
524 wheat display strong to moderate RCA values, representing 80% of the total exported
525 commodities. Wheat remains strategic for the country, especially in the EU28 market, with
526 the Czech Republic successfully competing with Germany and France, for instance. The
527 same pattern is present across east-central European countries for wheat.

528
529 Czech barley remains competitive in the European market, especially compared with
530 barley from neighboring countries (Germany, Austria, Slovakia, and Poland). Rapeseed
531 in the Czech Republic displays the greatest resilience across climate and impact
532 scenarios and is exceptionally competitive in both the European and global markets. The
533

a. No Climate Change

c. Regional

b. National

d. Global

■ Czech Republic ■ Rest of the World ■ West
■ North ■ South ■ Central East

534 **Fig. 5 Projected bilateral trade flows of crops aggregated in 2050 under the RCP8.5 scenario (in million tons)**
 535 **across four climate impact scenarios. (a) No climate change, (b) National impact, (c) Regional impact, and (d) Global**
 536 **impact. The colors represent regions, with the Czech Republic (green) as the focal area. The thickness of the connecting**
 537 **lines indicates the trade volume.**
 538

539 The Czech Republic remains among the top-performing countries in terms of this crop.
 540 Austria, Germany, and Italy are identified as the largest importers of Czech crop
 541 commodities.

542 In contrast, Czech imports from neighboring countries in east-central Europe range
543 between 1.8 and 1.9 million tons in the no climate change scenario and global climate
544 impact scenario, respectively. The RCA values of potatoes and maize are low, with values
545 for potatoes being less than 1 for the Czech Republic and those for maize being lower
546 than those for leading key players in the EU28, such as Germany, Slovakia, Hungary,
547 Slovenia, and Romania. The Czech Republic lags behind both the EU28 and global RCA
548 levels, highlighting its limited competitiveness in terms of maize production, with a value
549 of approximately 1. A comparative disadvantage is projected for potatoes in the Czech
550 Republic, where countries such as Poland and Belgium exhibit strong comparative
551 advantages both in the EU28 and globally. Slovakia and the Netherlands are the leading
552 exporters to the Czech Republic, where maize and potatoes represent 75% of the total
553 imports. When climate change impacts are isolated to the Czech Republic, the country is
554 projected to decrease the total export of crops by 6% and increase the total import of crops
555 by 5% compared with that in the no climate change scenario. When climate change
556 impacts are applied globally, the total export of crops increases by 6%, with total imports
557 projected to decrease by 5% by mid-century. The values for each commodity are shown
558 in Supplementary Tables 5 and 6.

559

560 **Comparison with global and European results**

561 Compared with the European Union, the Czech Republic faces more considerable
562 projected biophysical yield reductions than the global average. The EU28 region is
563 projected to experience relatively small reductions, mostly between -5% and -15%, while
564 the global impacts are expected to be even less severe, typically between -5% and -10%
565 (Supplementary Figs. 2-4, 6). Projected biophysical yields for wheat are more resilient
566 than those for maize, ranging from -15% to 1% in the EU28 and from -10% to 3% globally,
567 although variability increases under high-emission scenarios (RCP8.5) without CO₂
568 fertilization, for which the Czech Republic decline is up to -12%. The average biophysical
569 yield changes for the EU28 mask the heterogeneous impacts of climate change among
570 countries. As the level of warming increases from SSP1-2.6 to SSP5-8.5, yield impacts
571 become more extreme, particularly for some southern and eastern European countries.
572 Compared with other EU28 countries, the Czech Republic experiences relatively modest
573 yield changes, similar to those in other Central European countries, such as Poland
574 (Supplementary Fig. 6). The negative extreme effects are dominated by C4 crops such as
575 maize, with negative effects also expected in most other EU28 countries, with the most
576 severely affected countries being Italy, France, Croatia, and Slovenia. In contrast, wheat
577 shows a mixed pattern of impacts, with positive effects in some western and east-central
578 European countries and negative effects in some northern and eastern European
579 countries (Supplementary Figs. 3 and 6).

580 The larger reductions in the EU28 compared with the global average can be explained by
581 both climatic and structural factors. Climatic conditions in southern and eastern Europe
582 amplify negative impacts, whereas more temperate regions in central and western Europe
583 sometimes benefit. At the global level, however, trade reallocation across continents helps
584 buffer production losses, dampening the overall average. Crop type sensitivity further
585 explains these differences: C4 crops such as maize respond more negatively to high
586 temperatures, whereas C3 crops such as wheat display a broader range of outcomes.

588 Supplementary Figs. 8–10 show the economic responses to the effects of climate change
589 globally and in the EU28 under regional and global scenarios. Like the Czech Republic,
590 the EU28 is projected to experience more variability and severe impacts than those
591 observed globally. In contrast, price fluctuations stand out, with changes ranging from –
592 7.5% to +4.5% regionally and –5.0% to +3.2% globally. The consumer response becomes
593 more relevant at the EU28 level than at the Czech Republic level, with changes ranging
594 from –4% to 2% under regional impact scenarios and from –2.8% to +1.3% in the global
595 impact scenario. Yield and production are positively correlated with biophysical yields,
596 which are driven by climate impacts in the EU28 and market interactions. An inverse
597 relationship is observed for the EU28, as for the Czech Republic. Both climate and market
598 effects are greater in the global impact scenario than in the regional impact scenario.

599 The overall effect of climate change impacts in the EU28 is a decrease in production
600 despite shifts in management systems and area expansion. Changes in global indicators
601 are relatively minor, remaining mostly within $\pm 1\%$, except for prices, which display greater
602 variability, reaching up to 3%. Globally, trade adjustments and production compensate for
603 the regional effects of climate change, yet crop prices are expected to surge. As in the
604 EU28 and the Czech Republic, yield and production have a positive relationship with
605 biophysical yields, whereas area has an inverse relationship. Strong reallocation patterns
606 across regions, both in terms of management productivity and less so in terms of area,
607 help buffer losses in production due to climate change impacts globally.

608 **Discussion**

609 We applied a multilevel framework using two globally consistent models, GLOBIOM and
610 EPIC-IIASA, to evaluate how climate change affects Czech agriculture and how the
611 country responds through autonomous adaptation. Unlike earlier Czech studies, such as
612 that of Pohanková et al. (2022), which focused on biophysical outputs for specific crop
613 rotations, and other field-based projections, our approach links biophysical yield impacts
614 with economic and trade dynamics at the national scale. This allows us to move beyond
615 single-crop or site-level insights (e.g., Hlavinka et al., 2015) and align our analysis with
616 broader global frameworks. While previous intercomparison studies, such as that of
617 Jägermeyr et al. (2021), established similar patterns globally, our study uniquely traces
618 how yield changes in the Czech Republic are transmitted through international markets to
619 shape production, trade, and competitiveness. Importantly, we incorporate the latest
620 CMIP6 projections (Gier et al., 2024), providing a more realistic representation of carbon–
621 nitrogen interactions and land use dynamics. Our contribution also complements
622 emerging protocols that explicitly link local processes with global dynamics, such as the
623 framework of Poláková et al. (2025). In this context, our study demonstrates the novelty
624 of situating Czech agriculture within a multilevel framework, revealing adaptation
625 opportunities and risks that remain hidden in national-only assessments.

626 Our projections show that maize is more vulnerable to climate stress than wheat is,
627 particularly under high-emission scenarios, which is consistent with the findings of
628 Eitzinger et al. (2013) and Trnka et al. (2018). This aligns with the findings of Pohanková

629 et al. (2022) and Muench et al. (2024), who emphasized that potential yield gains depend
630 on management practices and farmer adoption of adaptation. We also find that national-
631 scale assessments may overestimate local yield shocks while underestimating the
632 buffering role of trade. Similar outcomes have been observed in Brazil (Zilli et al., 2020),
633 Gambia (Carr et al., 2024), the UK (Challinor et al. 2016), and Ireland (Adenaueer et al.,
634 2023). Importantly, our findings highlight transnational climate risks: yield shocks abroad
635 propagate through trade and prices to influence Czech production and competitiveness.
636 These findings echo studies on Europe's cross-border vulnerabilities, showing that
637 droughts or losses outside the EU can significantly affect its food security and economy
638 (Ercin et al., 2019; Ercin et al., 2021).

639 Land expansion emerged as the dominant autonomous adaptation strategy, especially
640 under global scenarios where price signals are transmitted via trade. This reflects the
641 relatively favorable land base of the Czech Republic, which is less affected by drought
642 than neighboring countries are (Eitzinger et al., 2013). However, the scope for expansion
643 is limited: under the common agricultural policy (CAP), the conversion of permanent
644 grassland is prohibited in protected areas and heavily restricted elsewhere (Ministry of
645 Agriculture of the Czech Republic 2022), and expansion would carry environmental costs,
646 including biodiversity loss, greenhouse gas emissions, and reduced ecosystem services
647 (Lorencová et al., 2013; Papadimitriou et al., 2019). Thus, while land expansion provides
648 an immediate buffer against yield shocks, it is unlikely to be sustainable. In practice,
649 adaptation relies more on reallocating within existing arable land, maintaining ecological
650 areas, adopting soil-conserving practices, and adjusting trade.

651 Reliance on a narrow set of commodities also increases vulnerability. Wheat, barley, and
652 rapeseed dominate Czech exports (e.g., beer, feed), and while they are well captured in
653 GLOBIOM, the model does not differentiate organic from conventional farming. This is
654 important, as organic farming is projected to reach 21% of land by 2028, and policy
655 measures aim to strengthen the fruit, vegetable, hops, wine, and apiculture sectors
656 (Ministry of Agriculture of the Czech Republic 2022). Planned adaptation is therefore being
657 reoriented toward soil, water, and biodiversity outcomes while sustaining competitiveness.
658 Crop diversification, combined with sustainable intensification, should complement land
659 expansion to enhance resilience and long-term competitiveness.

660 The implications of our results extend beyond production to the policy and institutional
661 dimensions of adaptation. CAP regulations protect grasslands, wetlands, and ecological
662 features, making large-scale expansion legally and economically difficult (Ministry of
663 Agriculture of the Czech Republic 2022). Farmers also face financial and practical
664 barriers, such as high upfront investments, uneven advisory support, and uncertainty over
665 climate and markets. Consequently, realistic adaptation pathways in the Czech Republic
666 will depend on CAP-compatible strategies such as reallocating existing arable land,
667 adopting soil-conserving practices, and diversifying into resilient or higher-value crops. At
668 the EU scale, production reallocation among member states helps buffer localized shocks
669 but generates distributional consequences across regions. Globally, trade integration
670 stabilizes supply and prices but exposes small open economies such as the Czech
671 Republic to risks from regulatory mismatches or sudden disruptions. National-only
672 assessments that ignore these dynamics risk maladaptation by overstating self-sufficiency

673 and underestimating the benefits and trade-offs of global integration. By embedding
674 Czech agriculture in a multilevel framework, our study shows that effective adaptation
675 requires attention to both domestic and transnational dimensions, providing a stronger
676 foundation for policies that enhance resilience while minimizing unintended trade-offs.

677 **Conclusion**

678
679 Our study contributes to the growing body of research that moves beyond isolated yield
680 projections toward systemic, multiscale assessments of agricultural resilience. By
681 situating Czech agriculture within a trade-mediated global context and complementing
682 recent advances in local-to-global modeling, we provide a novel perspective that better
683 captures both the opportunities and risks of autonomous adaptation. The results highlight
684 the importance of integrating global agricultural impacts and trade dynamics into national
685 climate change assessments. Accounting for international market interactions reveals
686 greater adaptive capacity for the Czech Republic than suggested by national-only
687 analyses, particularly through trade-driven responses and land use reallocation. However,
688 the heavy reliance on land expansion raises sustainability concerns, underscoring the
689 need for policies that balance adaptation with mitigation and environmental protection.
690 These findings reinforce the value of multiscale approaches for informing robust
691 adaptation planning. Policymakers should prioritize strategies that leverage trade and
692 market responses while advancing sustainable intensification and resource-efficient
693 practices. Overemphasis on self-sufficiency risks underestimating adaptation potential
694 and increasing vulnerability, whereas trade-based strategies can buffer national shocks,
695 increase resilience, and optimize resource use. For small, open economies such as the
696 Czech Republic, recognizing the interplay between domestic responses and transnational
697 climate risks is critical for achieving sustainable and effective adaptation.

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705
706

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715
716

717 **Author contributions**

718
719 JAG, PH and MT developed the conceptual framework; JAG and EB developed the
720 scenarios, methodological framework and improved the model (GLOBIOM). JAG wrote
721 the initial manuscript and performed the data analysis. MT, PH, EB, IPH and PAH edited
722 and commented on the manuscript. IPH and PAH contributed to the discussion with
723 JAG. MT supervised the project.

724
725 **Conflict of interest**

726 The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

727
728 **Data availability**

729 The code and data used in the scenario analyses are available from the corresponding
730 author upon request.

731

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939 **National climate change impact assessments underestimate the**
940 **potential of autonomous adaptation**

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981 **Supplementary Tables**

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983 **Supplementary Table 1** | References for each General Circulation Model used by EPIC-IIASA to project
 984 climate impacts on yield.

General Circulation models	Reference
GFDL-ESM4	(Dunne et al., 2020)
IPSL-CM6A-LR	(Boucher et al., 2020)
MPI-ESM1-2-HR	(Gutjahr et al., 2019)
MRI-ESM2-0	(Yukimoto et al., 2019)
UKESM1-0-LL	(Sellar et al., 2019)

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986 **Supplementary Table 2** | Mapping of maize, wheat, rice and soya yield simulations from EPIC to all crops
 987 in GLOBIOM.

GLOBIOM crop	Mapping
Cassava, groundnuts, rapeseed, sunflower, palm, chickpeas, cotton, potatoes, sweet potatoes, flax, fallow, peas	C ₃ crops are represented by the average climate impact of wheat, rice and soybean that are directly simulated
Oats, rye, triticale	Oats, rye, triticale yields are represented by wheat yield simulations.
Rice	Rice yield is directly simulated
Soybean	Soybean yield is directly simulated
Soft and durum wheat	Wheat yield is directly simulated
Maize and maize silage	Maize yield is directly simulated
Sugarcane, sugar beet	C ₄ crops are represented by maize yield directly
Millet, sorghum	Millet and sorghum are represented by half of the negative effects of maize yield
Barley	Barley yield is represented by half of the negative effects of wheat yield

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995 **Supplementary Table 3** |Regression coefficients (intercept and slope) for the Economic responses to
 996 biophysical yield changes in the Czech Republic under three climate impact scenarios (national, regional,
 997 and global) for 2050.

Variable	National		Regional		Global	
	Intercept	Slope	Intercept	Slope	Intercept	Slope
Yield	-0.28	0.91	-0.40	1.03	-0.35	1.05
Area	1.81	0.36	2.64	-0.75	3.13	-1.36

Variable	National		Regional		Global	
	Intercept	Slope	Intercept	Slope	Intercept	Slope
Production	1.55	1.27	2.17	0.35	2.66	-0.22
Consumption	0.33	0.12	0.22	-0.02	-0.01	-0.15
Exports	3.06	1.94	3.97	1.03	5.43	0.15
Imports	0.90	-1.03	-0.23	0.67	0.01	0.84
Prices	-1.21	-0.40	-1.40	-0.33	-0.75	-0.58

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Supplementary Table 3 | Impact of crops on supply (YIELD, AREA, PROD: production), demand (CONS: consumption) and market (EXPORTS, IMPORTS, PRICE) by 2050 in the Czech Republic across different climate change scenarios applying globally. The values are in % of change based on no climate change scenario.

CC scenario			CROP	Exogenous yield	Supply			Demand	Market		
CO2	RCP	GCM			YIELD	AREA	PROD*	CONS	EXPORTS	IMPORTS	PRICE
yes	RCP 2.6	Mean GCM ensemble	Wheat	0.63	0.58	0.00	0.58	-0.01	1.03	-11.22	-1.21
no	RCP 2.6			-1.55	-2.38	4.68	2.19	-0.23	7.01	12.66	1.61
yes	RCP 7.0			2.24	2.28	-0.40	1.87	0.01	4.59	0.51	-1.46
no	RCP 7.0			-2.22	-2.86	8.59	5.48	-0.26	13.23	-5.19	1.61
yes	RCP 8.5			0.62	0.12	2.69	2.82	-0.15	5.96	-3.78	-1.79
no	RCP 8.5			-5.70	-6.28	14.77	7.56	-0.45	18.61	-5.24	5.32
yes	RCP 8.5	GFDL-ESM4		2.61	2.63	-0.85	1.76	-0.10	5.66	11.70	-1.55
		IPSL-CM6A-LR		0.44	-0.38	3.24	2.86	-0.39	4.36	-31.18	-1.81
		MPI-ESM1-2-HR		1.43	1.37	-0.38	0.98	-0.15	2.50	-1.09	-0.34
		MRI-ESM2-0		3.48	3.06	-0.01	3.05	-0.21	8.60	8.05	-1.81
		UKESM1-0-LL		-5.00	-5.59	12.48	6.19	-0.25	5.66	-36.06	1.49
yes	RCP 2.6	Mean GCM ensemble		Rapeseed	0.62	0.66	0.04	0.70	0.00	0.45	-1.00
no	RCP 2.6		-1.56		-2.16	7.43	5.11	0.00	4.13	-3.02	2.99
yes	RCP 7.0		2.14		2.10	-0.17	1.93	0.00	1.20	-3.02	-0.46
no	RCP 7.0		-2.27		-2.31	12.01	9.43	0.00	7.34	-7.09	4.99
yes	RCP 8.5		0.52		-0.04	5.10	5.06	0.00	3.80	-4.57	1.91
no	RCP 8.5		-5.77		-4.74	18.83	13.20	0.00	10.05	-11.17	6.66
yes	RCP 8.5	GFDL-ESM4	2.50		2.44	-0.68	1.74	0.00	1.77	0.94	0.24
		IPSL-CM6A-LR	0.42		-0.12	4.43	4.31	0.00	3.21	-4.04	2.30

		MPI-ESM1-2-HR		3.57	2.44	-0.08	1.13	0.00	0.68	-1.90	-0.19
		MRI-ESM2-0		-5.37	3.33	1.52	4.90	0.00	3.52	-5.26	-1.46
		UKESM1-0-LL		1.35	-4.67	16.29	10.86	0.00	6.01	-21.34	5.69
yes	RCP 2.6	Mean GCM ensemble	Maize	-2.01	-2.08	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	5.66	5.05	2.50
no	RCP 2.6			-3.41	-3.49	-2.16	-2.26	-2.26	3.95	3.43	3.82
yes	RCP 7.0			-1.09	-1.14	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	5.33	5.05	2.37
no	RCP 7.0			-4.65	-4.75	-2.16	-2.26	-2.16	-0.69	-0.53	2.80
yes	RCP 8.5			-6.81	-6.90	-0.65	-0.68	-0.68	2.19	2.37	2.71
no	RCP 8.5			-11.72	-11.85	-2.12	-2.16	-2.16	-2.95	-1.69	0.13
yes	RCP 8.5	GFDL-ESM4		3.48	3.44	-0.08	-0.08	-0.08	1.88	1.04	1.94
		IPSL-CM6A-LR		-9.58	-9.64	-2.15	-2.23	-2.23	1.30	3.21	4.09
		MPI-ESM1-2-HR		-7.06	-7.23	-0.82	-0.81	-0.81	3.55	1.45	-0.07
		MRI-ESM2-0		-0.28	-0.34	-1.28	-1.33	-1.33	10.40	8.54	3.98
		UKESM1-0-LL		-21.68	-21.82	-2.14	-2.16	-2.16	2.30	4.24	3.84
yes	RCP 2.6	Mean GCM ensemble		Barley	0.69	0.64	-0.12	0.51	0.00	0.08	-8.70
no	RCP 2.6		-1.51		-1.26	6.08	4.75	0.00	9.41	-32.15	6.27
yes	RCP 7.0		2.54		2.66	-1.05	1.58	0.00	3.39	-6.45	-2.82
no	RCP 7.0		-2.08		-1.77	6.12	4.24	0.00	4.16	-57.02	10.82
yes	RCP 8.5		0.96		1.31	5.09	6.47	0.00	11.76	-41.87	1.21
no	RCP 8.5		-5.47		-5.26	7.13	1.49	0.00	-1.71	-49.04	18.42
yes	RCP 8.5	GFDL-ESM4	2.90		2.97	-1.11	1.82	0.00	7.15	12.56	-5.67
		IPSL-CM6A-LR	0.60		0.50	-1.31	-0.82	0.00	6.66	51.54	-2.10
		MPI-ESM1-2-HR	1.87		1.92	-1.04	0.86	0.00	-6.13	-56.02	-0.44
		MRI-ESM2-0	3.59		3.48	-1.79	1.64	0.00	6.22	6.88	-5.28
		UKESM1-0-LL	-4.30		-3.99	6.34	2.10	0.00	-3.51	-67.94	16.53
yes	RCP 2.6	Mean GCM ensemble	Potatoes		0.37	0.46	0.82	1.29	-0.01	5.27	0.59
no	RCP 2.6			-1.81	-1.70	0.91	-0.81	-0.03	-3.29	-0.46	0.68
yes	RCP 7.0			1.89	1.86	0.44	2.31	0.05	8.06	0.07	0.08
no	RCP 7.0			-2.46	-2.41	0.91	-1.52	-0.11	0.32	4.57	0.74
yes	RCP 8.5			0.15	0.10	0.05	0.15	-0.08	1.71	0.78	1.27
no	RCP 8.5			-6.15	-6.10	0.88	-5.27	-0.02	-9.86	7.55	0.67
yes	RCP 8.5	GFDL-ESM4		2.23	2.10	-1.13	0.95	-0.28	5.25	0.76	0.65
		IPSL-CM6A-LR		0.18	0.16	-0.36	-0.20	-0.41	5.60	4.16	2.21
		MPI-ESM1-2-HR		0.94	0.84	-0.25	0.58	-0.29	7.69	3.95	0.91
		MRI-ESM2-0		3.75	3.58	-0.07	3.51	0.52	12.41	1.64	-1.27

		UKESM1-0-LL		-6.49	-6.30	4.10	-2.46	-0.41	-6.34	0.73	2.57
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Supplementary Table 4 | Impact of livestock on supply (PROD: production), demand (CONS: consumption) and market (EXPORTS, IMPORTS, PRICE) by 2050 in the Czech Republic across different climate change scenarios applying globally. The values are in % of change based on no climate change scenario.

CC scenario				Supply	Demand	Market		
CO ₂	RCP	GCM		PROD	CONS	EXPORTS	IMPORTS	PRICE
yes	RCP 2.6	Mean GCM ensemble	Bovine meat	-0,01	0,00	-10,20	-1,34	1,42
no	RCP 2.6			-0,79	0,00	-10,60	0,95	0,95
yes	RCP 7.0			-0,03	0,00	-9,26	-1,16	-0,15
no	RCP 7.0			-0,79	0,00	-10,60	0,87	1,42
yes	RCP 8.5			-0,46	0,00	-11,16	-0,11	0,92
no	RCP 8.5			-0,77	0,00	-9,25	1,08	-0,25
yes	RCP 8.5	GFDL-ESM4		-0,02	0,00	-9,21	-1,17	0,36
		IPSL-CM6A-LR		-1,18	0,00	-11,16	2,05	1,09
		MPI-ESM1-2-HR		-0,17	0,00	-11,21	-1,01	0,82
		MRI-ESM2-0		-0,97	0,00	-11,16	1,41	1,10
		UKESM1-0-LL		-0,77	0,00	-10,19	0,95	0,61
yes	RCP 2.6	Mean GCM ensemble		Milk	-0,04	0,00	-0,16	0,00
no	RCP 2.6		-2,63		0,00	-10,12	0,00	0,72
yes	RCP 7.0		-0,10		0,00	-0,37	0,00	0,35
no	RCP 7.0		-2,63		0,00	-10,13	0,00	0,48
yes	RCP 8.5		-1,54		0,00	-5,94	0,00	0,48
no	RCP 8.5		-2,57		0,00	-9,90	0,00	0,76
yes	RCP 8.5	GFDL-ESM4	-0,08		0,00	-0,32	0,00	0,30
		IPSL-CM6A-LR	-3,93		0,00	-15,14	0,00	0,58
		MPI-ESM1-2-HR	-0,55		0,00	-2,13	0,00	0,06
		MRI-ESM2-0	-3,23		0,00	-12,43	0,00	0,21
		UKESM1-0-LL	-2,57		0,00	-9,83	1,19	0,98
yes	RCP 2.6	Mean GCM ensemble	Pig meat		0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
no	RCP 2.6			0,00	-1,68	0,77	-3,06	0,98
yes	RCP 7.0			0,00	0,00	0,67	0,05	-0,03
no	RCP 7.0			0,00	-1,68	3,21	-2,87	0,72
yes	RCP 8.5			0,00	0,00	2,33	0,18	-0,20
no	RCP 8.5			0,00	-1,68	3,21	-2,87	1,43
yes	RCP 8.5	GFDL-ESM4		0,00	0,00	1,98	0,15	-0,96
		IPSL-CM6A-LR		0,00	0,00	2,33	0,18	-1,04
		MPI-ESM1-2-HR		0,00	0,00	1,86	0,14	-0,14
		MRI-ESM2-0		0,00	0,00	1,11	0,09	-1,34

		UKESM1-0-LL		0,00	-1,68	3,56	-2,84	1,65
yes	RCP 2.6	Mean GCM ensemble	Poultry meat	0,00	0,00	0,11	0,01	0,19
no	RCP 2.6			0,01	0,00	-0,21	-0,04	0,98
yes	RCP 7.0			-0,01	0,00	7,31	0,86	-0,11
no	RCP 7.0			0,03	0,00	0,46	0,00	2,38
yes	RCP 8.5			0,02	0,00	0,80	0,06	0,37
no	RCP 8.5			0,00	0,00	-0,20	-2,70	3,03
yes	RCP 8.5	GFDL-ESM4		0,07	0,00	2,55	0,17	0,09
		IPSL-CM6A-LR		0,04	0,00	0,11	-0,07	0,76
		MPI-ESM1-2-HR		0,07	0,00	0,72	-0,04	0,20
		MRI-ESM2-0		-0,03	0,00	0,11	0,08	-0,61
		UKESM1-0-LL		0,03	-0,98	0,50	-2,66	2,69

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Supplementary Table 7 | Changes in average cropland, grassland and other natura land areas for the Czech Republic and the EU28 a relative to the no-climate-change baseline across RCP and GCM scenarios Results are presented for scenarios where climate impacts are applied only to the Czech Republic (national), the EU28 (regional) and to the entire world (global).

Czech Republic									
	Cropland area [%]			Grassland area [%]			Other natural land areas [%]		
Climate impact scenario	National	Regional	Global	National	Regional	Global	National	Regional	Global
Climate Scenario									
RCP 2.6	2.09	3.01	-0.07	-0.04	0.00	0.00	-12.68	-18.33	0.42
RCP 2.6 wo CO2	0.22	3.51	4.64	0.02	-0.04	-2.15	-1.31	-21.34	-24.40
RCP 7.0	2.67	0.47	-0.57	-0.04	0.01	0.02	-16.23	-2.87	3.41
RCP 7.0 wo CO2	0.04	4.44	7.11	0.00	-2.13	-2.15	-0.26	-23.32	-39.50
RCP 8.5	2.66	3.83	3.38	-1.54	-2.04	-2.04	-13.49	-19.73	-16.99
RCP 8.5 wo CO2	0.25	7.17	11.29	-0.02	-2.15	-2.15	-1.50	-39.83	-64.99
Average	1.32	3.74	4.30	-0.27	-1.06	-1.41	-7.58	-20.90	-23.68
EU28									
	Cropland area [%]			Grassland area [%]			Other natural land areas [%]		
Climate impact scenario	National	Regional	Global	National	Regional	Global	National	Regional	Global
Climate Scenario									
RCP 2.6	0.47	0.71	0.41	-0.08	-0.04	0.02	-4.82	-5.90	-14.37
RCP 2.6 wo CO2	0.37	0.90	1.63	-0.06	-0.11	-0.10	-3.24	-9.97	-19.85
RCP 7.0	0.43	0.44	0.01	-0.04	-0.08	-0.03	-3.91	-7.50	-33.04
RCP 7.0 wo CO2	0.26	1.35	1.97	-0.04	-0.13	-0.12	-2.43	-15.96	-4.21
RCP 8.5	0.58	0.88	0.75	-0.10	-0.08	-0.04	-5.92	-11.24	-5.67
RCP 8.5 wo CO2	0.44	1.96	3.36	-0.05	-0.14	-0.19	-4.13	-22.40	-10.28
Average	0.43	1.04	1.35	-0.06	-0.10	-0.08	-4.07	-12.16	-14.57

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Supplementary Table 8 | Average crop production and price impacts for the Czech Republic and the EU28 relative to the no climate change scenario across climate scenarios. Changes in production (top) and price (bottom) for major agricultural commodities are presented for scenarios where climate impacts are applied only to the Czech Republic (national), the EU28 (regional) and to the entire world (global).

Production						
	Czech Republic			EU28		
Climate impact scenario	National	Regional	Global	National	Regional	Global
Wheat	2.33	3.08	2.82	0.83	0.66	0.28
Maize	-0.08	-0.80	-0.68	-0.52	-0.46	-1.41
Barley	5.27	7.52	6.47	0.03	-0.40	-2.62
Rapeseed	3.82	5.50	5.06	1.37	0.90	2.07
Potatoes	-0.31	-0.22	0.15	-0.13	-0.41	-0.35
Prices						
	Czech Republic			EU28		
Climate impact scenario	National	Regional	Global	National	Regional	Global
Wheat	1.20	-1.10	-1.79	0.37	0.54	0.39
Maize	1.98	3.05	2.71	9.81	1.45	6.92
Barley	0.32	2.74	1.21	0.61	1.49	-0.55
Rapeseed	0.89	1.49	1.91	0.88	1.61	1.80
Potatoes	0.18	0.92	1.27	0.15	0.29	0.34

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Supplementary Table 9 | Intercept and slope coefficients for Supplementary Fig. 9 for the European Union + UK.

Climate impact scenario	National		Regional		Global	
Variable	Intercept	Slope	Intercept	Slope	Intercept	Slope
Yield	-0.14	2.48	-0.07	0.69	-0.06	0.73
Area	0.42	-0.79	0.40	-0.25	0.15	-0.44
Production	0.29	1.71	0.34	0.45	0.11	0.32
Consumption	0.24	0.16	0.18	0.15	0.33	0.20
Exports	0.56	5.24	-1.65	0.53	-2.81	0.33
Imports	0.37	-0.23	-1.91	-0.47	-1.73	-0.07
Prices	0.49	-1.63	0.69	-0.36	0.19	-0.58

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Supplementary Table 10 | Intercept and slope coefficients for Supplementary Fig. 9 for the world

Climate impact scenario	National		Regional		Global	
Variable	Intercept	Slope	Intercept	Slope	Intercept	Slope
Yield	0.01	-10.24	-0.09	-0.05	-0.32	0.28
Area	-0.04	10.08	0.04	0.14	0.43	-0.16
Production	-0.03	-0.15	-0.05	0.09	0.10	0.13
Consumption	-0.03	-0.15	-0.05	0.09	0.10	0.13
Prices	0.06	9.17	0.16	0.04	-0.56	-0.49

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1034 Supplementary Figures

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Supplementary Fig. 1| Regional classification of European countries and the rest of the world for the international trade analysis. The map categorizes the regions into the Czech Republic (green), Central East (pink), West (blue), North (purple), South (orange), and Rest of the World (yellow).

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 1046 **Supplementary Fig. 2** | Evolution of cereal and oilseed trade in the Czech Republic under climate impact
 1047 scenarios. Panels show projected imports and exports of (a) wheat, (b) rapeseed, and (c) barley between
 1048 2020 and 2050. Lines indicate mean changes across GCMs, with colors representing climate scenarios
 1049 (RCP2.6, RCP7.0, RCP8.5). Shaded ribbons denote the range of uncertainty across GCMs. Results are
 1050 shown for three of climate impact scenarios: National (CZ), Regional (EU28), and Global (World).
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 1053 **Supplementary Fig. 3** | Percentage change in biophysical crop aggregated yields under three Shared-
 1054 Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) - Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), calculated as averages
 1055 of General Circulation Models (GCMs): (a) SPP1- 2.6 (b) SSP3 - 7.0, and (c) SSP5 - 8.5 with CO₂ effect.
 1056 The x-axis represents individual countries and regions grouped geographically, while the y-axis shows
 1057 percentage yield changes relative to a non-climate-change scenario. The colors of the bars represented
 1058 EU28 regions used in the analysis of international trade.

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 1060 **Supplementary Fig. 4** | Percentage change in biophysical wheat aggregated yields under three Shared-
 1061 Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) - Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), calculated as averages
 1062 of General Circulation Models (GCMs): (a) SPP1- 2.6 (b) SSP3 - 7.0, and (c) SSP5 - 8.5 with CO₂ effect.
 1063 The x-axis represents individual countries and regions grouped geographically, while the y-axis shows
 1064 percentage yield changes relative to a non-climate-change scenario. The colors of the bars represented
 1065 EU28 regions used in the analysis of international trade.

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 1068 **Supplementary Fig. 5** | Percentage change in biophysical maize aggregated yields under three Shared-
 1069 Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) - Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), calculated as averages
 1070 of General Circulation Models (GCMs): (a) SPP1- 2.6 (b) SSP3 - 7.0, and (c) SSP5 - 8.5 with CO₂ effect.
 1071 The x-axis represents individual countries and regions grouped geographically, while the y-axis shows
 1072 percentage yield changes relative to a non-climate-change scenario. The colors of the bars represented
 1073 EU28 regions used in the analysis of international trade.

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Supplementary Fig. 6 | Revealed Comparative Advantage (RCA) for five key agricultural commodities (a: Wheat, b: Maize, c: Barley, d: Rapeseed, e: Potatoes) across the European Union (EU) countries, and the EU28 region under various climate impact scenarios. The RCA index reflects the relative export competitiveness of a country in a specific crop, with values above 1 indicating a comparative advantage. Different climate impact scenarios are represented by distinct symbols and different climate change scenarios by distinctive colors

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Supplementary Fig. 7 | Projected biophysical yield changes (%) with respect to the non-climate change scenario for wheat, maize, and aggregate crops in the European Union countries plus United Kingdom, and globally under different climate scenarios and General Circulation Models (GCMs). Bars represent GCM-averaged values.

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Supplementary Fig. 8 | Projected biophysical yield changes (%) with respect to the non-climate change scenario for wheat, maize, and aggregate crops in the Czech Republic, the European Union plus United Kingdom, and globally under different climate scenarios and General Circulation Models (GCMs). Bars represent GCM-averaged values, and individual points correspond to specific GCMs.

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 1102 **Supplementary Fig. 9** | Impact of regional and global climate scenarios on agricultural indicators for the
 1103 EU28 and the world. (a) Percentage changes in agricultural indicators for the EU28 under regional (gray)
 1104 and global (orange) climate impact scenarios. Indicators include yield, area, production, consumption, price,
 1105 imports, and exports. (b) Percentage changes in global agricultural indicators under the global climate
 1106 impact scenario (orange). Indicators include yield, area, production, consumption, and price.
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Supplementary Fig. 1 | Economic responses to biophysical yield changes under three climate impact scenarios (National, Regional, and Global) for 2050. Black dots represent changes in production, while colored lines indicate univariate regressions for selected variables: area (green), consumption (red), exports (orange), imports (IMPO), production (P), prices (dotted black) and biophysical yield (black) a) globally and b) in the European Union plus United Kingdom.

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 1122 **Supplementary Fig. 2** | Decomposition of climate change impacts, autonomous adaptations, and total
 1123 effects on crop production expressed as absolute changes relative to a no-climate-change scenario (in
 1124 1000 tons). It breaks down the results into three components: (1) Climatic impact (CC) – changes in
 1125 productivity due to biophysical effects, (2) Autonomous adaptations (MGMT) – adjustments through shifts
 1126 in agricultural management systems, and (3) Total impact (PROD) – combined effects on crop production,
 1127 including changes in yield (TOT YLD) and cropland area (TOT AREA) under different climate impact
 1128 scenario: (a) in the European Union plus United Kingdom, (b) in the World. Bars represent projections
 1129 under the UKESM1-0-LL RCP 8.5 scenario, with error bars indicating variability across GCMs x RCP
 1130 combinations. Black dots show results excluding CO₂ fertilization effects.
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1132 **References**

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